

Mapping the suggestion of EAT:

“the minister of health and the minister of agriculture should talk to each other!”

An exercise on the why such suggestion makes sense for sustainability

Did you know that the sum of global food waste is equivalent to the land use of whole China? That in the last decades, in the whole world, the biggest toll was taken by farmers, who remain or get poor, while food business is still profitable? That already two years ago, UK had problems importing tomatoes or Norway importing rice because of exceptional droughts in the countries of origin? Did you know that in Scandinavia about 10% of the income is spent on food, versus 90% in the poorest countries? Did you know about the simultaneously existing 800 million of undernourished people and the other millions of obese people, that show that there is a general sign of poor distribution, poor food quality and social un-sustainability in our global food system? Is a smiley label all it takes to change our consumer behavior towards discarding fruit?

Tonight, I got the chance to attend the event Future for Food, at the MESH in OSLO, and learn this, and much more. From distribution to consumption to waste, I could hear and learn about different points of view in business. And this was the right place to be, if you ever wondered what these experts had to say on challenging questions as: *Should it all be the consumers' responsibility? What motivates a shift in businesses taking actions? What can policy makers change? What do consumers accept? Do you want ultimately your business, that is working to solve problems, to eventually become obsolete?*

It was moderated by **Annabelle Lefébure-Henriksen**, CEO at [Fairtrade Norge](#). The invited speakers were **Olav Kjørven**, Chief Strategy Officer of [EAT Foundation](#), a non-profit whose mission is to change our relationships to food in a way that is healthy both for us and the planet, engaging 40 cities to implement the EAT targets; **Bendik Walderhaug**, Head of Sales of the food-waste tackling start-up [Too Good To Go](#) present now in 13 countries and connecting 30000 restaurants, and **Dyveke Elset**, Sustainability Communications Adviser at [NorgesGruppen ASA](#), the main food importer and distributor in Norway.

They met around the idea about the need of making our food chain – from production to consumption more sustainable in all ways – environmentally, socially and economically, and gave interesting insights in the current situation.

Hear what insights and highlights we got for that day's exchanges.

All agreed that collaboration is essential to solve global problems, a “**coalition of the willing**” is the best way to not have the status quo go on. A status quo, as we are reminded, where the primary producers suffer most and get a shrinking part of the cake in the business of the food chain. For now, some collaborations exist, as the actions of EAT describe, between different academic disciplines, partnerships along the food chain. However, it still has to become a habit, as many stakeholders still remain “each in their own silo”. Cities seem to be the best size to start for the change: they are small enough to allow for relatively fast changes, but big enough for the changes to have a real impact, motivating further applications in other places. Businesses in the food distribution are bound to include in their annual reports a sustainability report in all their areas of responsibility – socially, as they employ many people, environmentally, as their business, between agriculture and transport, is a major GHG emitter, as well as ethically, and of course economically. But to get to that point, where sustainability is an important point in the business and even business model of some enterprises, mentalities had to change, and still many challenges are present in our society. While a few years ago it was sensitive for a supermarket to report waste, as it was understood as a sign of unsold items and bad business, it is now a pride to contribute to fight waste, with TooGoodToGo as a partner. Transparency is vital also on the side of the acquisition of goods, to know about the provenience, for ethical, social or environmental reasons. The responsibility of the consumer is engaged, as he has the choice over his purchases, both for his own health, and to guide the purchases of the chains he is buying at. “the shops only offer what consumers want” is an often-heard logic. However, is that the end of the question? Will a business have the courage to risk to be boycotted because of common product that does not look a certain way, are consumers in rich countries “spoiled” by a large choice of ever-fresh produce year-round, all day long? Will they accept that due to major failure in a country, their rice or tomatoes will lack in their supermarket? Distributors need some that take the risk to try a new model, show that it is working, that they are not losing their income, to motivate them to change. For example, the action halving the price of less fresh goods at the end of the day actually increased purchases and lessened waste for the shops, but it had to be tried somewhere before it became more common. Pure marketing ideas, as putting a smile on the face of a banana to “save the single banana” from being forgotten and wasted... is consumer behavior maybe easily shaped after all? Additionally, policy is a key actor, whose action should drive change instead of supporting the status quo. Linking policies that are now separated, like for instance health policies and agricultural policies. Innovative ideas about doctors prescribing food or farmers getting a share of the money saved on health care by a better nutrition of the general population are some further ways to explore...

How to decide on a partnership and to share about this strategy in a visual way?

Defenders of the Nature, or alarmed researchers on the impact of biodiversity loss make their voices loud to preserve resources that are essential to many human activities. But investments are still low and actions reflect the place environment holds in priority ranking – certainly not the top ranks, for citizens and governments alike, despite some changing. There seem to be more important issues to tackle, like health, and getting enough food. Moreover, farmers have often a simple survival need before they would even care for the environment. “Green” will not pay the bills, will it?

Why are there so many prototypes of great ideas, as we do not have the time for just prototypes?

In a government’s perspective, choosing between priorities, to satisfy not only voters but also a wide range of other stakeholders, is a difficult balance exercise.

But, as one of the goals for the SDGs 2030, partnership development can help answer some of those dilemmas. Or, as EAT Chief Strategy Officer suggested “*the minister of health and the minister of agriculture should talk to each other!*”.

To see how partnerships make sense, and how the complexity of decision making within a government can be managed, mapping can be an useful tool. In particular, we will use Wardley maps as a base to lay out the suggestion of linking policies that are now separated - for instance health policies and agricultural policies.

Public health in an universal healthcare system

The map shows straightforward need chains between stakeholders, practices and concepts with a logical link. We can base this links on the point of view of the government. So, the government needs voters to get to power and to pay taxes. Voters need to survive, hence their need for health. Health itself is sustained by healthcare in form of treatment, facilities and preventive care.

All those need a budget, handled by a ministry of health from the government, payed partly by taxes from voters. For treatment, natural resources might be used. Technical resources are needed for treatment, facilities and preventive care.

Simplified map of the public health care system (adapted from Wardley maps, p 356, fig 239)

In the same manner, we can map the food system from the government's perspective. Like previously, the government needs voters to get to power and to pay taxes. Voters need to survive, so they need access to food. That food comes from food distribution and processing industry, which gets its raw material from farms. Farms, to produce their products, need natural, technical and financial resources. Government needs voters (and satisfy food industry), so gives subsidies to farms. This needs a budget, handled by a ministry of agriculture from the government, financed partly by taxes.

Simplified map of the food system

Similarly, we can map environmental management from the government's perspective. Like previously, the government needs voters to get to power and to pay taxes. In this case, specific, targeted taxes are not well defined or less spread, or even inexistent. For environmental issues, the connection between voters and their needs are not clear: status, romantic, general well-being, cause to defend, or research specialty. To simplify, we call it fulfillment, to differentiate it from survival needs. This class of voters might not be a majority, but since this movement is gaining momentum, it is somehow important to care for the environment (natural resources) to get these voters satisfied. So nature conservation and sustainable practices – which might be financing research projects - would be a response. This needs some form of technical resources to implement. It also depends upon a budget, handled by a ministry of environment from the government, financed partly by taxes. But if global voters care for nature per se is still relatively low, taxes are low and budget is low, too. Practices are likely not much developed

Simplified map of the environmental management

Now, it is worth noticing the common points (in red) between those three maps: in all cases, the government is the anchor point; therefore voters (citizens) are also a key point, as their need to survive. And natural resources are somehow involved also.

If we merge those three maps into one, we get a map that can look messy at first sight.

For better visualization, specific “routes” or “silos” – namely health, environment and agriculture are respectively blue, green and yellow; red are still the common points.

To ease our representation, we will remove “fulfilment” need, and merge the three different “taxes” points.

In this new map, new links can be made visible:

In point (1): A wide range of literature documents the link between Health and food, describing unhealthy vs healthy food habits and consumption. Indeed, the nature of food has an impact of the health, both long-term and mid-term, generally grouped under the term “civilization diseases” – diabetes, obesity, cardiovascular diseases to name a few.

Moreover, health is also influenced by quality of food. In this case, it is closely connected to farming practice, linked to technical resources used – as harmful chemical entrants as phytochemicals, or from natural resources, as pollutants. Another connection comes to food processing industry, especially if the distribution and processing industry is lacking quality or is not well established: food preservation issues, contaminations or simple lack of food (undernourishment, malnutrition) due to distribution problems.

In point (2) we can represent how Health is also connected to natural resources and their state of conservation or preservation (loss of environmental services as air filtration, or heat mitigation, pollution)

Finally, we can highlight the fact that natural resources conservation are a basic need in all three chosen ministries (overseen by same government), which is an important point to make.

This representation ultimately allows discussion of reality and visualization of future steps to take. For instance in point (3), we can allow a flow from one budget to another, to compensate for imbalance or lack of targeted taxes, which is nothing very novel.

Moreover, a quantified feedback of food effects on health as linked in point (1) can calculate positive effects of some sorts of foods on health, thus reducing needs for certain treatments, reducing occupation of facilities and acting as preventive care measures. This diminishes budget need for some treatments, a budget that can be redirected in form of subsidies to encourage and spread certain nature of foods and quality of foods. This encourages the spread of sustainable practices (point (4)), facilitating their implementation, their improvement. Eventually, they can become a common practice (utility) in farms for instance.

Could be extended to social cost tourism etc

One other interesting fact emerging from the map is, the government does not need to care about how small or big fraction of the population is, that needs “act for environmental causes” (“fulfilment”), as this need is indirectly satisfied by covering basic survival needs connected to health and food. Likewise, taxes and budgets allowing flows or merged does allow to maneuver the rhetoric of taxes, i.e. not adding “new” taxes for environmental issues, as there were something unrelated, but just improve the existing food and health system with existing resources. Innovative ideas about doctors prescribing food or farmers getting a share of the money saved on health care by a better nutrition of the general population are just some ways to explore...

So what are our take-away message for the future of food? Waste less, choose wisely what you eat for your own good, those can be questions left to the consumer to handle. But changing the way food is produced requires higher and broader involvement, by increasing partnerships.